

ARABIC STUDENTS' PREFERENCES IN CHOOSING REFERENCES FOR THESIS WRITING

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this article is to investigate the PBA UINSA students' preferences of Indonesian references over Arabic references, despite the fact that their theses are entirely written in Arabic. This study used a qualitative research method. The data collection techniques performed by observation, interviews, and documentation. The findings of this study revealed that the problems faced by the students of PBA at UINSA in choosing references were as follows: the themes and methods chosen greatly influenced the choice of references, a lack of foreign language vocabulary mastered caused students the need to use Indonesian references, and many references accessible in Indonesian language related to the learning process in Indonesia during the pandemic. Furthermore, when writing the thesis, particularly in the methodology section, it was found that a number of references were taken from Indonesian sources. This was done because employing Indonesian references made the subject easier to understand than using foreign-language references.

KEYWORDS

Arabic learning, Arabic teaching, Arabic writing, references

INTRODUCTION

Writing plays a significant part in the academic success of someone who is enrolled at the university level. If it is observed that almost all learning is related to writing, this is due to the fact that writing is a component that students are required to complete as part of the formal requirements for the scientific atmosphere of the academic environment. Additionally, writing is one of the requirements that must be met in order to fulfill the formal requirements for the academic environment. Therefore, it is very important for students to get used to writing as early as possible by paying attention to the rules of writing good and correct scientific papers. This activity requires a lot of effort from students in order for them to be able to examine the topic that is going to be written about, which is why it is so important for students to get used to writing. The completion of a thesis under the guidance and aid of a faculty advisor is one of the requirements that students need to fulfill in order to be eligible for a bachelor's degree. Students must also have a minimum GPA of 2.0. (Arifin, 2006).

Students in the Arabic Language Education Program/*Pendidikan Bahasa Arab* (PBA) at UIN Sunan Ampel Surabaya (UINSA), where they are not used to reading literature written in Arabic because it is difficult for them to understand the contents of the writing that the author is trying to convey, appear to find writing a thesis to be a very stressful and nerve-wracking experience. This is due to the fact that students lack the skills necessary to write an Arabic thesis, which is a fear in itself and creates a sense of reluctance to do it. Arabic includes numerous linguistic characteristics and the interrelationships of parts that must be mastered, therefore it is understandable that students find it challenging to speak the language. However, the primary reason for this difficulty is the linguistic issue. These components

include knowledge of nahwu, sharaf, balaghah, ashwat, as well as a variety of translations and other topics, all of which are interrelated (Norlaila & Ahmad, 2018).

According to Nurgiyantoro's (2012) statement, writing is an activity that a person engages in with the purpose of communicating his thoughts through a language. Writing is an activity that encourages creativity and self-expression; thus, in order to be a writer, you need to be able to include terminology and be an expert in writing and language structure (Nurgiyantoro, 2012). Writing is a skill, so in order for students to write an Arabic thesis, they are required to first master a large quantity of vocabulary words. However, they cannot just stop there; they must also be able to assemble sentences using the vocabulary that they have mastered, and of course the language structure must be correct.

The lack of seriousness shown when searching for reference sources is another significant issue that negatively impacts the quality of student theses. This can be seen in the numerous theses written by students majoring in Arabic Language Education who take quotes from journals and books written in Indonesian even though the thesis they are writing is in Arabic. It is normal for us to be aware that reference sources need to be comprehensive in order for them to be suitable to be used to support arguments. Furthermore, reference sources are the primary foundation of a scientific paper, and for students, this contributes significantly to the completion of academic assignments (Sumiyati & Arif, 2004).

This situation is undoubtedly reason for worry due to the fact that those involved are individuals who have expressed an interest in teaching Arabic in the future and are expected to become qualified educators. The students' ability to write in Arabic, or *maharah kitabah*, is demonstrated by their production of the thesis writing in Arabic. To be successful in the field of Arabic education, student needs to be fluent in a number of language skills, including speaking, reading, listening, and writing. As a result of the fact that it is necessary for students to be able to demonstrate proficiency in all four language skills (Sakhliid, 2012).

Some researchers have conducted a variety of investigations on this subject over the course of time. Yaqin's (2015) research investigates the factors that contribute to the inadequate utilization of English-language reference materials in the composition of library science theses (Yaqin, 2015). Latent Problems of Thesis of English Education Students is the title of a study that was carried out by Pratama (2017). This study was also published in 2017. In a separate piece of research, Sukandi and Rianita (2018) looked at the challenges faced by Indonesian EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students when it came to the process of writing their theses in the area of English pedagogy (Sukandi & Rianita, 2020).

Students in the PBA UINSA have to write a thesis in Arabic as part of their coursework. Students obviously have challenges while attempting to use Arabic reference materials due to this provision. According to the aforementioned background, the aim of this study is to investigate the factors that lead students to utilize allusions to the Indonesian language in their Arabic theses.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The government has stipulated in the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 49 of 2014 concerning National Higher Education Standards Article 45 paragraph 4, that the final project in the form of a thesis, thesis, or dissertation is a form of research that can be carried out by students by adhering to certain

standards and procedures. Students are exposed to a wide variety of scientific works due to the fact that during their time as students, they are almost always tasked with completing a variety of assignments that require them to conduct research, conduct analysis, and present their findings and arguments regarding a particular issue. Before students can begin working on a scientific paper, there are, of course, a great many other supplementary things that need to be prepared on their end in order to ensure that the study goes swimmingly and without any hiccups.

The development of scientific activity is precipitated by the appearance of a problem, and in order for researchers to discover a solution to the problem, they need to grasp the root of the problem by comprehending a number of different theories in order to formulate new ways of thinking. In order to prevent the newly acquired information from becoming specialized information, it is necessary to modify it so that it is applicable to the real circumstances that exist in the field. Obtaining data from the field may be done in a number of different methods, including through observation, interviews, exams, and the completion of questionnaires. Following the development of the facts and the theory, the researcher will arrive at new conclusions, and it will then be the researcher's responsibility to create a solution based on those findings (Kurniadi, 2017).

The production of a high-quality scientific paper requires strong writing abilities; nonetheless, colleges continue to struggle with the challenge of being able to create scientific papers for their student bodies. The students' general lack of interest in reading is one of numerous variables that contribute to the decline in their writing abilities. According to information that was made public by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IAEEA) in 2007, it was revealed that the reading ability of students in Indonesia is on par with that of students in South Africa and New Zealand (Siswati, 2017). Reading, on the other hand, is one of the most important factors in developing one's writing skills. This is due to the fact that, unconsciously, a person has acquired a great deal of information, experience, comparing perspectives, and even knowledge as a consequence of the reading that they have done. The reader may also be unaware of the development of language skills, such as a vast vocabulary, the recognition of various forms of sentences, and so on, which results in the reader becoming increasingly rich in language. Another thing that the reader may be unaware of is the development of language skills (Baarid & Yusuf, 2021).

Reading comprehension, the ability to think critically, and self-control have all been hypothesized to have some sort of connection or bearing on one another and on one's capacity for scientific writing. Establishing a connection between scientific writing and reader comprehension. Comprehension of what one has read is of utmost significance when it comes to the process of writing. Text comprehension is necessary for evaluating information sources in terms of reading, comprehending, reading objectives, sorting portions of the text, paraphrasing the text, merging information, producing summaries, and synthesizing writing (Wahyuni S, 2016).

Writing scientifically in a paradigmatic manner involves a procedure that involves conveying intelligent ideas with careful language and presenting them with accurate writing approaches as legitimate support. When writing scientific papers, it is important to pay attention to numerous aspects of presentation. These aspects include five things: topic formulation, literature study, research methodology, language usage, and writing approaches (Mujiyanto, 2006). According to the viewpoint of Dewojati, a piece of written work may be classified as

scientific if it presents scientific concepts and argues that these concepts are backed by facts, references, analysis, and specific research methods (Dewojati, 2012).

In this study, Yaqin (2015) used qualitative research methods to investigate the factors that led to the low use of English-language reference sources in the writing of library science theses. His research focused on researching the factors that led to the low use of English-language reference sources. Within the scope of this study are a few of the issues that contribute to the anxiety that students feel when it comes to writing their theses. First, there is a lack of expertise in performing basic research in secondary school, and subsequently the same problem develops in higher education. This is the first difficulty. The next issue is that students don't have much of an interest in reading as a result of a number of factors, including the fact that the lesson plan and the assignments given by the teachers do not require students to read and the ease with which students can gain access to the internet, which enables students to play more games. The students' poor writing skills, combined with the fact that they don't have much of an interest in reading on their own, makes their writing skills worse. In addition, the most significant factor that contributes to the low quality of student theses is the fact that students do not make a concerted effort to find references that are in line with the content that they have read and researched. Therefore, the authors examine the extent to which the use of English-language reference sources in thesis writing at the Department of Library Science at UIN Sunan Kalijaga Yogyakarta and the inhibiting factors, and the findings of the study found that this is caused by the low ability of students in using English. The authors of the study also found that the factors inhibiting the use of English-language reference sources in thesis writing are: In addition, there is a lack of desire on the part of professors to encourage students to make use of reference sources written in English (Yaqin, 2015).

Following that is the investigation that was carried out by Hendi Pratama when he was working as a lecturer at a state university. Hendi Pratama did an in-depth analysis of 75 theses that were written by students in the Department of English Education. The purpose of this research is to establish whether or not there has been a recent deterioration in the quality of the theses produced by students in the Department of English Education. It is believed that the findings of this research may assist lessen the difficulties experienced by students majoring in education, particularly those majoring in the English Department or other education-related fields who have difficulties comparable to those described here. During the course of his investigation, he discovered ten underlying issues that were present in the theses written by students majoring in English education. In addition to that, the researcher has come up with a total of four suggestions that may be utilized to solve this issue. In the study, qualitative methods of document analysis were combined with straightforward descriptive statistics. The information is taken from the system that manages the library's archives. The discovery of the phenomenon known as "copying templates" is by far the most common challenge that students encounter when they are working on their theses. One of the challenges that students face is that the topic of their thesis is too heavily influenced by teaching strategies. Another challenge is that students are less willing to investigate other areas of study. Students working on theses look to examples of previous theses and replace the subject of their study only marginally.

Sukandi and Rianita (2018) conducted another study in which they investigated the challenges that Indonesian EFL students face when writing theses in the field of English Language Education. The researchers used qualitative research methods and discovered that the difficulties in writing theses were, for the most part, unique to each individual. On the

other hand, the degree to which this condition is impacted by the individuals' perspectives on the nature of thesis writing and the manner in which a process approach, as opposed to a product approach, should be used to them. The conclusion of this research highlights how vital it is to use a constructivist paradigm while overseeing students' actions in the process of writing their theses. This approach asserts that students actively create their own knowledge and emphasizes the concept that it focuses on mental processes, acknowledging students' settings, life experiences, and cultural schemas as important factors in the construction of students' understandings. In the subject of English Education, the researcher highlights that it is far more essential to pay attention to the process of writing the thesis than it is to pay attention to the thesis itself as a standalone result. It is essential to take a process-oriented approach while monitoring and assessing theses; doing so will, it is hoped, prevent students from squandering their time and resources by submitting plagiarized work, which would ultimately result in their failing the course (Sukandi & Rianita, 2020).

This study aims to determine the cause of Indonesian language references being used more by PBA students in Arabic theses, which is the difference between this study and other studies. The conclusion that can be drawn from the previous studies is that the use of reference sources written in a language other than the thesis language is still an important problem. This study focused on the low use of reference sources in writing Arabic theses in the Arabic Language Education Study Program. Previously, the majority of the previous research discussed the low use of reference sources in English, and some researchers conducted research that was not on English Education Study Program. In contrast, this study examined the low use of reference sources in English.

RESEARCH METHODS

Because the objective of this study is to examine students' behaviour, the type of research technique that was utilized in this study was a qualitative. This was done because a qualitative research method is the type of research method that is most suited for the purpose of this study. Research that is qualitative does not rely on mathematical logic, number principles, or statistical methods; rather, qualitative research seeks to analyze the nature of human patterns and behavior without reducing them to quantitative substances. This type of research aims to understand human behavior and patterns without reducing them to numbers (Mulyana, 2006). The use of a qualitative methodology in this research is beneficial since it allows for the collection of more, more specific data on the challenges that PBA UINSA students have when attempting to employ reference materials in their theses.

The researchers divide the data sources used in this investigation into two categories: main data and secondary data. This is done so that they may obtain responses that are appropriate to the subject matter that is being investigated. The theses written by PBA students at UINSA and housed in the institution's library serve as primary sources of data that are collected. Naturally, the researchers only restrict the research topic in this study based on particular characteristics, specifically students who would graduate between the years 2020 and 2022. In the same vein, the researchers will only consider theses that were written within the same time period as the study that will be conducted on them. These constraints are imposed on the research in order to facilitate the researchers' work and reduce the overall scope of the investigation. While researchers relied on interviews and observations with PBA UINSA students who had already finished their theses to compile secondary data, they also use a number of research techniques.

In order to compile their findings, the researchers employed a number of techniques, including observation, interviews, and documentation. Because observation is the cornerstone of all scientific inquiry, the researchers in this study employ a methodology known as participatory observation, in which the researchers also take part in the same kinds of activities that are being researched in order to ensure that the data collected is more exhaustive, factual, and provides an understanding of how this phenomenon can take place (Sugiyono, 2018). In this particular instance, the researchers additionally created an Arabic thesis in order to ensure that they were able to comprehend and experience the same things that were encountered by the human sources that were observed during this investigation.

This study makes use of an in-depth interview, which differs from structured interviews in that it is conducted in a more relaxed manner. The purpose of this interview is to uncover problems in an unrestricted manner by posing questions to interviewees and soliciting their feedback, as well as suggestions and viewpoints from those who are interviewed (Sugiyono, 2018). After getting to know each other well, the researchers conducted direct interviews and asked questions about the informants' difficulties in compiling Arabic thesis, as well as factors that influence the selection of Indonesian-language reference sources while the thesis was being written. Before conducting interviews with interviewees, the researchers took a personal approach so that the informants would feel comfortable and more open, thereby increasing the reliability of the information obtained. After conducting interviews with interviewees, the researchers will present their findings in the form of a thesis.

The researchers in this study collected several theses that were written by PBA UINSA students in the years 2020 to 2022. Theses were uploaded to an online library website, which can be accessed through the page located at www.digilib.uinsby.ac.id. The researchers used the documentation method to conduct this study. After that, the researchers looked at the reference source data that the students had utilized, and they discovered that the vast majority of the references had been taken from Indonesian publications like books and journals.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Numbers of Research Written by Students and the References Used

The following phases of analysis were carried out by the researchers, and each one served as a step in the process of generating study results. The researchers began their work by conducting a study of 10 theses authored by UINSA PBA students between the years 2020 and 2022 and preserved in the UINSA digital library. The researcher took a close look at the reference materials that the students had used in their theses in order to determine the extent to which the students had employed references from Indonesian and Arabic sources. Second, the following stage, which was interviews, the researchers spoke with ten students who had compiled their theses between the years 2020 and 2022.

As part of the first stage of study, the researcher read and examined 10 theses authored by UINSA PBA students between the years 2020 and 2022 and kept in the UINSA digital library. The researcher paid particular attention to the following three aspects of each thesis: 1) The total number of references in Indonesian, 2) The total number of references in Arabic, and 3) The overall subject of the thesis.

The following table presents the findings obtained by the researchers based on their observations:

Table 1. Classification of PBA student thesis in 2020-2022

Nr.	Year	Thesis Title	Number of References in Arabic	Number of References in Indonesian
1	2020	Analisis kontrasif antara bahasa Arab dan bahasa Indonesia segi fi'il ma'lum dan fi'il majhul dan manfaatnya dalam pembelajaran bahasa Arab	16	7
2	2021	Efektivitas penggunaan strategi menghidupkan suasana belajar (<i>Lightening the Learning Climate</i>) dengan media pembelajaran busuu dalam meningkatkan keterampilan menulis mata pelajaran bahasa Arab berbasis daring	13	34
3	2021	Media pembelajaran Slideshare dalam meningkatkan keterampilan menulis siswa	5	26
4	2021	Efektivitas penerapan metode SQ9R dengan menggunakan media game edukasi online (<i>Crossword Puzzle Maker</i>) untuk meningkatkan kemampuan membaca siswa kelas X MA Ma'arif NU Assa'adah Bungah Gresik	5	25
5	2020	Analisis kontrasif antara bahasa Indonesia dan bahasa Arab mengenai bab tanda baca dan afiks pembentuk verba serta manfaatnya dalam pembelajaran keterampilan menulis	23	17
6	2020	Model pembelajaran <i>concept sentence</i> dengan permainan peti menulis untuk meningkatkan keterampilan siswa	10	21

7	2022	Efektivitas penerapan aplikasi <i>Google Duo</i> untuk meningkatkan maharah istima' kelas X MAN Sidoarjo	12	30
8	2021	Analisis konten kitab Mutholaah juz 1	8	7
9	2020	Penerapan, bentuk dan faktor-faktor pendukung dan pengganggu e-learning pada proses pembelajaran bahasa Arab	5	10
10	2020	Analisis kesalahan nahwu shorof dalam pembelajaran keterampilan menulis	24	21

According to the information presented in Table 1 above, it is possible to see that four of the ten theses that were analyzed made use of more references in Arabic. The thesis that made use of the most references in Arabic was titled as follows: analysis of *nahwu shorof* errors in learning writing skills, content analysis of the book Mutholaah juz 1, contrastive analysis between Indonesian and Arabic regarding the verb-forming affixes and their uses in Arabic teaching. All of these themes are related to classroom action research.

The titles of the remaining six theses are as follows: (1) *Efektivitas Penggunaan Strategi Menghidupkan Suasana Belajar* (Lightening the Learning Climate) *dengan media pembelajaran busuu dalam meningkatkan keterampilan menulis mata pelajaran bahasa Arab berbasis daring*, (2) *Media pembelajaran Slideshare dalam meningkatkan keterampilan menulis siswa*, (3) *Efektivitas penerapan metode SQ9R dengan menggunakan media game edukasi online (Crossword Puzzle Maker) untuk meningkatkan kemampuan membaca siswa kelas X MA Ma'arif NU Assa'adah Bungah Gresik*, (4) *Model pembelajaran concept sentence dengan permainan peti menulis untuk meningkatkan keterampilan siswa, penerapan*, (5) *Bentuk dan faktor-faktor pendukung dan pengganggu e-learning pada proses pembelajaran bahasa Arab*, (6) *Efektivitas penerapan aplikasi Google Duo untuk meningkatkan maharah istima' kelas X MAN Sidoarjo*. Each of the six theses is also an example of classroom action research, and they also make use of quantitative research methodologies.

Research that uses more Arabic reference sources is research that uses qualitative methods, and the themes taken are feasibility analysis of a book, analysis of writing errors, and analysis of book content; working on a thesis on this theme requires a lot of theory. This can be seen by looking at the classification that was presented earlier. from a wide range of Arabic works of literature in order to get accurate results from the research. Theses with the theme of developing learning media and using qualitative research methods are the ones

that use Indonesian language reference sources. Theses with this theme require more action in the classroom, and the theory that supports this research most commonly comes from books written in Indonesian.

According to these findings, the researchers came to the conclusion that one of the reasons for the low use of Arabic reference sources in the writing of the theses of PBA UINSA students was influenced by the chosen theme and research method. This was due to the fact that after conducting further analysis of the thesis data obtained, the researcher found that out of the four theses using more Arabic reference sources, these are theses with the theme of content feasibility analysis and nahwu shorof error analysis, where the r value was significantly higher. Research in Indonesia is conducted using qualitative approaches.

Factors Influencing the Students' Preferences

After interviewing, the ten PBA graduates from the range of 2020-2022 who have already earned their degrees reached to the conclusion that it is correct that in the process of putting together an Arabic thesis, they ran into obstacles or difficulties while selecting a reference source. The choice of Indonesian sources rather than Arabic sources by many of them is attributable to a number of factors, including the following:

To begin, in order to properly prepare Arabic thesis, one must, of course, first be able to understand what they have written. While many of them, in their theses, examine the efficacy of a medium or a method, which is then related to pre-existing learning theories, we are aware that numerous research quite similar to this one have also been conducted in Indonesia. Students are able to comprehend it better because to the numerous previous investigations, and they may then apply this comprehension to their own study. In the meanwhile, it goes without saying that pupils are required to first translate the reference into Arabic before attempting to comprehend it. Due to the fact that many pupils still have a limited vocabulary, they continue to find it challenging to interpret a large number of references before evaluating their meaning.

Infitah reported that one of the interviewees said the following:

"Kosa kata yang kami miliki tidaklah banyak. Jadi dalam pemilihan referensi tentu kami memilih sumber rujukan yang paling mudah kami mengerti dan yang paling mudah kami dapati. Dalam hal ini yakni rujukan yang berbahasa Indonesia."

"We don't have a lot of vocabulary. Therefore, while selecting references, we make sure to pick the reference sources that are not only simple for us to comprehend but also simple to locate. This ensures that the references we use are reliable and accurate. The reference is made in Indonesian in this particular instance."

According to Arifah Nargis, a graduate student from the year 2022, she disclosed the following information:

"Sebelum mengerjakan skripsi tentu kita memiliki skripsi-skripsi terdahulu yang kita jadikan sebagai pegangan. Biasanya skripsi tersebut memiliki kesamaan dengan judul skripsi yang kita pilih seperti dibagian media pembelajaran yang dipilih atau teori yang digunakan. Jadi, terkadang kita juga melihat pada bagian referensi yang juga bisa kita gunakan. Adapun dari skripsi-skripsi terdahulu masih banyak yang menggunakan referensi yang berbahasa Indonesia."

"Before working on the thesis, of course we have past theses that we utilize as a guide. Typically, the thesis will have elements that are comparable to the topic of the thesis that we pick, such as the section on the various learning medium that was chosen or the theory that was implemented. Therefore, there are times when we also glance at the reference section, which contains information that we may also utilize. When it comes to the theses that came before, there are still a lot of people who cite references in Indonesian."

Secondly, as a result of the coronavirus, the time period in which the thesis is being written—between the years 2020 and 2022—is the transition phase from a traditional offline learning system to an online learning system. They are obliged to use educational internet material that has been proven to be beneficial to the process of learning Arabic. Naturally, there are not yet a lot of references in Arabic that go into detail on the many different forms of internet media that are appropriate for use in the process of learning Arabic, and this is especially true in Indonesia.

According to Habibatul Nabila:

"Karena saya mengambil PTK (Penelitian Tindakan Kelas) maka pengambilan referensi berbahasa Indonesia lebih memudahkan bagi saya. Sebab sudah ada banyak jurnal-jurnal Bahasa Indonesia yang meneliti pembelajaran dalam sekolah semasa pandemi. Jika mencari jurnal yang berbahasa asing tentu masih terasa sulit karena melihat bedanya sistem pembelajaran di Indonesia dan yang ada di luar Indonesia."

"Due to the fact that I participated in CAR (Classroom Action Research), it was more simpler for me to take the Indonesian language references. mainly due to the fact that there are already a great number of articles written in Indonesian that examine learning in schools throughout the epidemic. When you compare the education systems in Indonesia with those in other countries, it is clear that there is a significant gap between the two. If you are interested in looking for journals written in foreign languages, this will, of course, continue to be a challenging task.

Third, in the section on research methods, it is a given that the majority of students are acquainted with the well-known authors of research technique books, which are resources that students frequently consult even before beginning to write a thesis. Of course, the majority of the numerous theses written on the theoretical foundation and research methodologies are supplemented by references. Because of this reason, references to Indonesian sources are frequently found in Arabic student theses.

Moch. Abdur Rohman, one of the respondent, said that:

"Karena yang saya tahu saat dulu ada mata kuliah metodologi penelitian hampir semua mahasiswa angkatan saya menggunakan buku Suharsimi Arikunto sebagai referensi. Hal tersebut tentu sangat berpengaruh saat saya mengerjakan skripsi"

"Because of what I know, virtually all of the students in my batch utilized the book written by Suharsimi Arikunto as a reference. When I am working on the thesis, this is without a doubt a highly important factor."

There are a number of books that, in addition to Suharsimi Arikunto, are utilized by the vast majority of PBA students. According to what Ihda Aini said:

"Selain buku Suharsimi Arikunto juga terdapat salah satu buku yang biasa dipakai mayoritas angkatan 17' yakni buku yang dikarang oleh Sugiyono. Saat mengerjakan skripsi hampir

semua skripsi yang jadi pegangan saya terdapat referensi dari buku Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D yang disusun oleh Sugiono”

"In addition to the book written by Suharsimi Arikunto, there is also another book that is extensively utilized by the batch of 17. This book is the one that was written by Sugiyono." During the time that I was working on the thesis, nearly all of the theses that ended up serving as my guide had references to the book Quantitative, Qualitative, and R & D Research Methods that is written by Sugiono.

CONCLUSION

It is possible to draw the following conclusion based on the outcomes of this study: PBA students have some difficulty in making use of Arabic references while they are writing Arabic thesis. Students in the PBA program are confronted with three challenges: the themes and methods selected have a significant impact on the students' decisions regarding the references they use for their research; the students' inability to master a sufficient amount of vocabulary in a foreign language forces them to make use of references written in Indonesian; and there are a great deal of Indonesian references that can be accessed that are related to the education system in Indonesia at the time of the pandemic. In addition, when working on the thesis, namely the section on research technique, I came across a lot of sources written in Indonesian. This was done because utilizing references in the Indonesian language made the subject much simpler to comprehend compared to using references in foreign languages.

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